

Supplemental Figure 1

SI Figure 1: Apoptosis detection in the small and large intestine by TUNEL assay.

Representative images and quantification of TUNEL positive cells (green) of the (A) duodenum (B) jejunum and (C) ileum show a significant increase in epithelial cell apoptosis in HDE exposed mice (Mann Whitney U, $p=0.0202$; $n=2$). This effect is reduced in the (D) proximal (unpaired t-test, $p=0.1656$; $n=4$) and (E) distal colon (Mann Whitney U, $p=0.6674$; $n=3-4$). The sex of each mouse is depicted by the data point color (light/pink (female) or light/blue (male)).